

TERMINOLOGICAL DICTIONARIES AS A SPECIAL TYPE OF DICTIONARIES IN THE TRADITIONS OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK LINGUISTICS

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Experts suggest dividing the parameters of the dictionary and the factors influencing the process of its creation into lexicographic and external factors. The first group of factors is determined by the needs of the user, while the second group reflects the opportunities that arise with the vocabulary. In order for the dictionary to fully satisfy the needs of the user, its design and structure should be created based on lexicographic factors.

The main condition for conducting a lexicographic analysis of any dictionary is the intersection of the parameters of the mega structure of the dictionary (relationships between the components and external structures of the dictionary (introduction), instructions for using the dictionary, content, abbreviations, etc. list, etc.) and the macro structure of the reference (the location of each item, the size of the main words in the vocabulary corpus) and the micro structure of the reference (the way the material is arranged) in special dictionary entries).

A definition of the word (term) is one of the basic elements of a dictionary. Usually, an explanatory dictionary article has the following structure: 1. main word; 2. phonetic description, 3. grammatical characteristics; 4. main word semantics; 5. the combining ability of the main word; 6. the ability to form words; 7. etymological information; 8. illustrative examples; 9. lexicographic explanation; 10. encyclopedic information; 11. link¹.

The macrostructure of the dictionary is the structure related to the general structure of the dictionary. As its components V. Dubichinsky "Introduction word", "Alphabet structure", "Ideographic structure", "Right side of the dictionary", "Left side of the dictionary", "Dictionary indicators" lists parts like².

Left and right parts of a vocabulary article. Vocabulary material, more precisely, one of the characteristic features of a dictionary article is their

¹Дубичинский В.В. Теоретическая и практическая лексикография. – Вена-Харковь, 1998. – 160 с. – С.90

²Дубичинский В.В. Теоретическая и практическая лексикография. – Вена-Харковь, 1998. – 160 с. – С.90

respective "left" and "right" parts, that is, a list of certain units and information about these units. is division. According to I.S. Kudashev, the traditional interpretation, such as the glossary on the "left side" and the explanation of word combinations on the "right side", creates a number of theoretical problems. First, this rule cannot be applied to units of "one-sided dictionaries" ("right-sided dictionaries") - spelling, morpheme, orthoepic, frequency, and reverse dictionaries. Second, if a dictionary article is divided into components or nested, it becomes difficult to calculate the actual number of descriptive units. Most lexicographers believe that whatever concept the author of the dictionary intends to explain based on the purpose of the dictionary, that information is on the left side, regardless of where the rest of the information is located in the dictionary. , suggests considering this information as the "right side".

I.S. Kudashev stated that the "right part" of the dictionary includes not only the right part of the dictionary article, but also any information about the units of the left part, as well as units located outside the main part of the dictionary: the title, includes information in the introduction, additional comments, and indicators. According to him, this interpretation of the right part leads to the solution of the problem of "one-sided dictionaries"; helps to see the content and construction of a dictionary article and other parts of the dictionary in one context. In the sources, the following types of units are included in the left part of the dictionary article as an object of traditional lexicography³:

- 1) small units of a word: morpheme, sema, term elements;
- 2) units larger than words: fixed phrase, free phrase, slang, cliché, stamp, etc.;
- 3) structural units of the lexical system: synonymous line, antonymic pair, homonymic and paronymic chains, whole-fragment and word formation nests, etc.;
- 4) speech units;
- 5) artificial language units, traditional signs and formulas;
- 6) graphic elements (for example, a picture dictionary, a dictionary of gestures)

Thus, modern dictionaries can have various types of units on the left side. However, the nature of the units that can be represented in the left part of the terminological dictionary, as well as certain restrictions on their composition, is explained by the fact that the elements of the left side must represent a certain

³Кудашев И.С. Проектирование переводческих словарей специальной лексики // Helsinki University Translation Studies. – Monographs 3. – Helsinki, 2007. – 445 с. – С. 36

system, however, in this place "equating systematic" and "lexical systematicity" is incorrect. P.N. Denisov writes: "... a dictionary is not a collection of random and approximate words of the vocabulary, but a work that is a lexical system or a microsystem. Despite the fact that in practical lexicography there are dictionaries of hundreds of difficult words and educational translation dictionaries covering several thousand words, they theoretically contradict the theory of changing the vocabulary of the language⁴. It is known from the lexicographical experience that, in addition to linguistic factors, extralinguistic, pragmatic, subjective and other factors also play an important role in the formation of a dictionary.

The lexicographic description of the system of terms related to real estate activity involves the implementation of a number of mandatory steps, one of which is the lexicographic analysis of existing terminological dictionaries. Lexicographic analysis of dictionaries, on the one hand, is carried out in order to determine modern methods of registration, fixation and description of terms related to real estate activity in existing dictionary sources. On the other hand, the results of the research allow to develop a single scientific concept that will be the basis of the dictionary, which is of interest not only as a means of obtaining information about the meanings and features of use, but also about the nature of the relevant part of the terminology related to real estate activity serves as material for the development of theoretical knowledge.

The analysis of modern manuals is carried out precisely in accordance with the methodology of lexicographic analysis and the scope of sources, the addressee, the criteria for choosing terms in the dictionary and the methods of their description are studied. The results of the lexicographic analysis, together with the requests of users and experts, determine the needs and requirements of the dictionary user, which reflects the terminology of real estate.

The most complete list of lexicographic parameters was presented for the first time in Y. N. Karaulov's article "On a trend in modern lexicographic practice"⁵. For example, language(s), introduction, chronological parameters, quantity, orthographic feature, word length, stress, number, verb type, transitivity, accentuation, tense, morpheme composition of the word (morphological bo 'linishi'), derivative parameters are distinguished as lexicographic parameters. S. V. Grinev's book "Introduction to Terminological Lexicography" contains

⁴ Денисов П.Н. Лексика русского языка и принципы ее описания. – 2-е изд., перераб. и доп. – М.: Рус. яз., 1993. – 245 с. – С. 210

⁵ Караулов Ю.Н. Лингвистическое конструирование и тезаурус литературного языка. – М., 1981. – С. 152-153.

information about areal, syntagmatic, illustrative, stylistic parameters, synonymous, associative, bibliographic and other parameters of the terminological dictionary from the point of view of macro and microstructure⁶.

References:

1. Дубичинский В.В. Теоретическая и практическая лексикография. – Вена-Харковь, 1998. – 160 с. – С.90
2. Кудашев И.С. Проектирование переводческих словарей специальной лексики // Helsinki University Translation Studies. – Monographs 3. – Helsinki, 2007. – 445 с. – С. 36
3. Денисов П.Н. Лексика русского языка и принципы ее описания. – 2-е изд., перераб. и доп. – М.: Рус. яз., 1993. – 245 с. – С. 210

⁶Гринев С.В. Введение в терминографию: Как просто и легко составить словарь. Учебное пособие. – 3-е изд., доп. – М.: Либроком, 2009. – 224 с.

